

Hydrogen-assisted self-ignition of propane-air mixtures in catalytic micro-combustor in the sequential feed mode

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ABSTRACT

Hydrogen-assisted self-ignition of propane-air mixtures in the sequential feed mode was investigated numerically in Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalytic micro-combustors. The computational results indicate that, the time taken to reach steady state, the hydrogen cut-off time, the propane ignition time and the cumulative propane emissions increased with increasing wall thermal conductivity; the self-ignition characteristics are similar to partially preheating the initial segment of the micro-combustor for low and moderate conductive walls; however, the self-ignition characteristics are close to completely heating the micro-combustor wall for high-conductivity walls. The minimum cumulative amount of hydrogen usage and minimization of startup time are discussed.

Keyword: micro-combustion; ignition characteristics; catalytic combustion; self-ignition; hydrogen-assisted ignition

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, there has been a dramatic increase in the number of military, consumer, and industrial applications utilizing portable electronic equipment, such as cellular telephones, laptops, and personal data assistants [1]. All of these devices require a portable power source, which is provided by batteries. For many of these applications, however, the relatively low energy density of traditional batteries imposes burdensome weight and power limitations on system design. Furthermore, most of these battery chemistries rely on materials that are difficult to recycle and environmentally damaging to dispose of. In addition, the highest energy density batteries are often non-rechargeable. These single-use batteries present especially challenging environmental, logistical, and economic burdens for in-field military applications where there is limited infrastructure for battery supply and disposal [2].

Power generation utilizing hydrocarbons offers a promising alternative to traditional batteries. The energy density of hydrocarbons is significantly higher than that of batteries (approximately 40 MJ kg⁻¹ versus 0.5 MJ kg⁻¹ for lithium-ion battery chemistries). In addition, hydrocarbon-based power systems can be quickly and repeatedly “recharged” simply by physical addition of more fuel [3]. Micro-combustors may play a vital role in the portable production of energy. The small scales in micro-combustors result in lower combustion temperatures due to enhanced heat-transfer coefficients [4, 5]. Finally, micro-combustors can also serve as efficient sources of heat for endothermic reactions, such as steam reforming and ammonia decomposition, in integrated micro-chemical systems for the production of hydrogen for fuel cell applications [6, 7].

Unfortunately, the benefits arising at the micro-scale are overshadowed by major difficulties in creating working micro-combustors. The two primary mechanisms for quenching in these systems are thermal and radical quenching [8, 9]. Increased heat-transfer coefficients are inherent to micro-scales, because for a fixed *Nusselt* number, the heat-transfer coefficient scales with

the inverse of the length scale. The high heat-transfer rates increase the heat lost from the reaction, reducing the operating temperatures and causing the flame to extinguish. In addition, the increased mass transfer within the micro-scale system, coupled with the high surface-area-to-volume ratio, results in radical adsorption onto the walls, followed by radical recombination. This dearth of radicals quenches the homogeneous chemistry [10, 11]. Another mechanism for loss of stability is blowout, which occurs when the burner exit velocity exceeds the flame burning velocity [12, 13]. In this case, the reaction front shifts downstream with increasing velocity and eventually exits the burner. The competition between the shifting of the reaction zone and thermal quenching has been observed in elliptic models of micro-scale systems for methane [14] and meso-scale systems for propane [15].

The self-ignition nature of hydrogen/air mixtures at the small scale of ceramic burners offers an opportunity to self-ignite hydrocarbons, which referred to as hydrogen-assisted self-ignition [16]. This concept may be a way toward elimination of ignition sources from micro-scale devices leading to further reduction of system size. Furthermore, since hydrogen is a main target for fuel cell applications, one can envision storage of small amounts of hydrogen during device operation from reforming of hydrocarbons that is subsequently used for startup. A significant aspect of catalytic micro-combustion of hydrogen over the noble metal catalysts is that the reaction rates are extremely fast and the reaction has low activation energy. Norton and Vlachos [17] explored the self-ignite propane-air mixtures with the assistance of hydrogen addition in confined ceramic micro-channels with Pt catalyst. They found that hydrogen-air mixtures self-ignite over a wide range of compositions. Propane kinetically inhibits hydrogen catalytic combustion at low hydrogen fractions. The minimum hydrogen composition for self-ignition of propane/air mixture compositions is found to be relatively constant, irrespective of propane composition. Yan et al. [18] demonstrated the self-ignition behavior of hydrogen, and numerically investigated

hydrogen-assisted ignition of methane-air mixtures in catalytic micro-combustors with a channel gap of 2.2 mm. The results showed that methane conversion rate decreases as the inlet velocity increases. The most suitable inlet velocity was 0.2 m/s, while the inlet temperature was 900 K. The ignition temperature will decrease considerably when hydrogen content of the fuel was increased with a fixed value of equivalent ratio, meanwhile, the moment of the ignition temperature advances and methane conversion rate also rises accordingly. Zhong et al. [19] experimentally investigated external heating and hydrogen-assisted catalytic ignition characteristics of n-butane (n-C₄H₁₀) in a Pt-coated monolith catalytic reactor, and discussed the chemical effect of hydrogen on hydrogen-assisted ignition, two startup methods and thermal insulation. They found that hydrogen has a positive chemical effect on hydrogen-assisted ignition, and high hydrogen mole fraction is favorable to hydrogen-assisted ignition. The co-feed method (n-butane/air/hydrogen mixtures are fed into reactor) and thermal insulation were found to be beneficial to hydrogen-assisted ignition. Furthermore, they also experimentally and numerically investigated the catalytic ignition processes and kinetics of hydrogen-assisted n-butane on Pt surface to reveal the catalytic ignition mechanism [19-21]. The results showed that the effect of hydrogen on the catalytic ignition process and temperature of n-butane depends on the concentration of hydrogen added. During hydrogen-assisted catalytic ignition of n-butane-air mixtures, hydrogen not only has a thermal effect, but a chemical effect as well [19]. The thermal effect is exhibited when small fractions of hydrogen are added. However, it is changed into chemical effect as the concentration of hydrogen is increased [20]. The concentration ranges of hydrogen with different effects were also predicted. The critical concentration value of hydrogen required for n-butane catalytic ignition is 0.025 on a molar basis [21]. Deutschmann et al. [22] studied hydrogen assisted catalytic combustion of methane on platinum experimentally and numerically. In the experiment, they measured the exit temperatures of methane/hydrogen/air mixtures flowing at atmospheric pressure through platinum coated honeycomb channels. Furthermore, they performed a one-dimensional time-dependent simulation of a stagnation flow configuration to elucidate the elementary processes occurring during catalytic ignition in the mixtures studied. They found that the dependence of the hydrogen assisted light-off of methane on hydrogen and on methane concentrations is discussed. The light-off is primarily determined by the catalyst temperature that is a result of the heat release due to catalytic hydrogen oxidation. Increasing hydrogen addition ensures light-off, decreasing hydrogen addition requires an increasing methane feed for light-off.

Most current prototypes of micro-combustors depend on exterior heating to generate energy for ignition, and the additional equipment necessary to power the exterior heaters can negate mass advantages of micro-combustors. The main objective of the present work is to investigate the hydrogen-assisted self-ignition of propane-air mixtures in the sequential feed mode in catalytic micro-combustors. The effect of catalytic chemical kinetics on self-ignition of micro-combustors is delineated. Finally, the minimum cumulative amount of hydrogen usage and minimization of startup time are explored.

2. Numerical models and simulation approach

2.1. Model geometry and mesh

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the micro-channel geometry.

A schematic view of the catalytic micro-combustor modeled in this work is shown in Fig. 1. The kinetics module plug-in for FLUENT was employed to simulate the flow of hydrogen-propane-air mixtures in the plane channel of height $H = 0.2$ mm, length $L = 20.0$ mm, and solid wall thickness $\delta = 0.2$ mm. The wall material is refractory ceramics SiC, which thermal conductivity k_s , the emissivity ε , density ρ and specific heat capacity c are 20 W/m·K, 0.8, 3.2×10^3 kg/m³ and 800 J/kg·K, respectively. Inner horizontal surfaces of micro-channel contained Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst washcoat. The properties of Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ supported noble metal catalysts are shown in Table 1. For all scenarios analyzed, the uniform grid size of 0.005 mm was used to mesh the computational domain.

Table 1 The properties of Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst washcoat

Property	Value
catalyst surface site density Γ (mol/cm ²)	2.7×10^{-9}
average pore diameter d_{pore} (m)	2.08×10^{-8}
catalyst porosity ε_{cat}	0.4
catalyst tortuosity τ_{cat}	8.0

In the present work, in order to couple the hetero-/homogeneous chemical kinetics, fluid dynamics, and heat transfer, FLUENT-KINETICS was employed to simulate the chemical kinetics.

2.2. Chemical kinetics for hydrogen combustion

The kinetics of hydrogen oxidation on noble metals has been extensively investigated in recent years, and detailed mean-field catalytic reaction mechanisms have been constructed [23-26]. Moreover, experimental and numerical studies have assessed the impact of homogeneous kinetics and of the hetero-/homogeneous chemistry coupling on the combustion of hydrogen or hydrogen-containing fuels over noble metals [27-32]. The chemical kinetics for the micro-combustion of hydrogen-air is adopted from Bui *et al.* [33], who developed the model via the hierarchical model reduction of 13-step surface catalytic reaction mechanism. The resulting reaction rate of micro-combustion is given by the following reduced-order reaction rate kinetics:

$$-r_{\text{cat, H}_2} = \eta A_0 T^\beta e^{-\frac{E_{\text{a, H}_2}^{\text{ads}}}{RT}} C_{\text{H}_2} \quad (1)$$

where the effectiveness factor η is 1, the pre-exponential factor A_0 is 1280 cm K^{0.5}·s⁻¹, the temperature exponent β is 0.5, and the activation energy $E_{\text{a, H}_2}^{\text{ads}}$ is 0 kJ·mol⁻¹ because of hydrogen adsorption is the non-activated process [33].

Norton *et al.* [34] reported that homogeneous combustion of near-stoichiometric hydrogen-air mixtures occurs in the larger gap size of 1.0 mm, but not for the smaller gap size of 0.25 mm. Even in the 1.0 mm micro-combustor, hydrogen light-off in gas phase was observed beyond the equivalence ratio ϕ_{H_2} of 0.33. In addition, Norton *et al.* [34] also reported that the above-mentioned kinetic model is valid for the concentration of hydrogen in the range of the equivalence ratio $0.008 < \phi_{\text{H}_2} < 0.424$. Mantzaras [35]

observed hydrogen light-off in gas phase for the equivalence ratio φ_{H_2} of 0.2 in 1.2 mm diameter micro-channels. Therefore, in this study, homogeneous combustion of hydrogen-air mixtures is neglected and Numerical simulations are restricted for hydrogen concentrations below the equivalence ratio φ_{H_2} of 0.2.

2.3. Chemical kinetics for propane combustion

In the present work, Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalysts were adopted for catalytic micro-combustion of propane-air mixtures. The reason is that the propane conversion of the noble metal catalysts decreases in the order Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ > Pd/ γ -Al₂O₃ > Rh/ γ -Al₂O₃ at the stoichiometric propane-oxygen ratio [36]. The reduced-order reaction rate kinetics for catalytic micro-combustion of propane-air mixtures are as follows:

$$r_{\text{cat}, C_3H_8} = \frac{k_{C_3H_8}^{\text{ads}} C_{s, C_3H_8}}{\left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{k_{O_2}^{\text{ads}} C_{s, O_2}}{k_{O_2}^{\text{des}}}}\right)^2} \quad (2)$$

where r_{cat, C_3H_8} is the surface catalytic reaction rate of propane. $C_{s, i}$ is concentration of adsorbed species i . k_i is adsorption or desorption rate constant of species i , and determined as follows:

$$k_i^{\text{ads}} = \frac{s_0}{\Gamma} \sqrt{\frac{RT}{2\pi M_i}} \left(\frac{T}{T_{\text{ref}}}\right)^{\beta_i^{\text{ads}}} e^{-\frac{E_{a,i}^{\text{ads}}}{RT}} \quad (3)$$

$$k_i^{\text{des}} = A_0 \left(\frac{T}{T_{\text{ref}}}\right)^{\beta_i^{\text{des}}} e^{-\frac{E_{a,i}^{\text{des}}}{RT}} \quad (4)$$

where s_0 is the sticking coefficient. Γ is Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst surface site density. M_i is the molecular weight of species i . T_{ref} is the temperature of reference conditions. The values of kinetic parameters for the catalytic combustion of lean propane are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 kinetic parameters for the catalytic combustion of lean propane over Pt/ γ -Al₂O₃

	A_0 (s ⁻¹) or s_0	β	E_a (kcal·mol ⁻¹)
C ₃ H ₈ adsorption	0.06	0.154	4
O ₂ adsorption	0.0542	0.766	0
O ₂ desorption	8.41×10 ¹²	-0.796	*

$$* E_{a, O_2}^{\text{des}} = 52.8 - \frac{2.3T}{300} - 32.0\theta_{O_2}$$

Surface area factor $\eta = 1.7$, the temperature of reference conditions $T_{\text{ref}} = 300$ K.

The activation energy $E_{a, O_2}(\text{des})$ of oxygen desorption depends on the coverage θ_{O_2} of oxygen radical, which is calculated as follows:

$$\theta_{O_2} = 1 - \frac{1}{\left(1 + \sqrt{\frac{k_{O_2}^{\text{ads}} C_{s, O_2}}{k_{O_2}^{\text{des}}}}\right)} \quad (5)$$

2.4. Boundary conditions

The incoming flow of hydrogen-air or hydrogen-propane-air mixtures was fully premixed and have uniform inlet temperature T_{in} of 300 K. The thermal boundary condition on the wall is the heat loss to the ambient air. The heat losses to the surroundings are calculated using the following equation

$$q = h(T_{w, o} - T_{\infty}) + \varepsilon\delta(T_{w, o}^4 - T_{\infty}^4) \quad (6)$$

Where the exterior convective heat transfer coefficient h is 20 W/m²·K in this study. $T_{w, o}$ is the temperature at the exterior wall surface. The ambient temperature T_{∞} is 300K. The solid wall emissivity ε is taken to be 0.8 and δ is the Stefan-Boltzmann constant.

2.4. Computation scheme

The quasisteady assumption necessitates gas-phase convective and diffusive timescales shorter than the solid heat conduction timescale, such that the gaseous flow can equilibrate to the channel wall temperature at any time during the transient start-up process [37-39]. The two-dimensional steady flow solver is coupled to a one-dimensional transient model for the solid heat conduction

Uniform profiles for the species mass fractions, temperature and axial velocity are applied to the inlet, while zero-Neumann conditions are set at the outlet and symmetry plane. No-slip is used for both velocity components at the gas-wall catalytic interface. The flow equations are discretized by a finite volume approach and a solution is obtained with a PISO method for the pressure-velocity field. The transient solid energy equation is solved with a second-order accurate, fully implicit scheme and a quadratic backward time discretization. The integration time step is fixed. A solution for the coupled flow and solid phase equations is obtained at each time step iteratively: convergence is reached when the solid temperature at all axial positions does not vary between successive iterations by more than 10⁻⁵ K. This results in up to 8000 iterations per time step.

The integration time step is selected to satisfy the QSS approximation, entailing convection, diffusion and characteristic chemical reaction times shorter than the corresponding solid heat conduction times. When such criteria are satisfied, the QSS approximation yields excellent agreement with full DNS [40]. According to the Michelin *et al.* [38] timescale analysis, the integration time steps of 5.0 ms are selected. This time step is sufficiently short to resolve the axial heat conduction in the solid and at the same time long enough to allow for equilibration of the gas-phase transport and chemical processes.

3. Ignition characteristics of hydrogen-assisted propane

In the present work, transient response in the sequential feed mode is analyzed: switched from hydrogen-air to propane-air mixtures. Hydrogen-air mixtures at the desired equivalence ratio are fed into the micro-combustor firstly. Once the sufficiently high temperature (ignition temperature of propane) in micro-combustor is reached, the hydrogen feed is cut off and the feed of propane-air mixtures is started. Simultaneously, keep total flow rate constant. The thermal effect of hydrogen on hydrogen-assisted catalytic ignition is the main influence factor, because the concentration of hydrogen added is low [41-46]. Therefore, the chemical effect is not consider in this work. Due to absence of detailed reaction mechanism of hydrogen-assisted catalytic ignition of propane-air mixtures, the variation of free radicals and the effect of hydrogen on the ignition temperature of propane are also not investigated.

3.1 H₂ requirement for C₃H₈ ignition

Fig. 2 The minimum equivalence ratio of H_2 required for the C_3H_8 ignition of a particular equivalence ratio $\phi_{C_3H_8}$ for different inlet velocities.

In the sequential feed mode, effect of equivalence ratio $\phi_{C_3H_8}$ on the minimum equivalence ratio of H_2 required for C_3H_8 ignition for different inlet velocities is shown in Fig. 2. As the equivalence ratio $\phi_{C_3H_8}$ is increased, the minimum concentration of H_2 required for C_3H_8 ignition decreases. For higher inlet velocity, the concentration of H_2 required for C_3H_8 ignition is expected to be lower in agreement with the previous section. The region below each curve represents that the H_2 concentration is insufficient for C_3H_8 ignition. While the above-mentioned behavior is existent at higher C_3H_8 equivalence ratio ($\phi_{C_3H_8} > 0.73$), the situation is entirely different at lower C_3H_8 equivalence ratio ($\phi_{C_3H_8} < 0.64$). Note that the wall temperature is still higher as the velocity is increased, keeping equivalence ratio constant. However, the location of the combustion zone is pushed downstream at higher inlet velocities. This prevents stabilization of propane combustion when we switch over from hydrogen-air to propane-air inlet. Hence, we see a reversal in the trend at lower propane equivalence ratio.

(a) Minimum concentration of H_2 required

(b) Exit wall temperature

Fig. 3 Effect of wall thermal conductivity on exit wall temperature and the minimum concentration of H_2 required for C_3H_8 ignition for different inlet velocities.

The effect of wall thermal conductivity on exit wall temperature and the minimum concentration of H_2 required for C_3H_8 ignition for different inlet velocities are shown in Fig. 3. The exit wall temperature is the minimum wall temperature that should be attained before switching from hydrogen-air to propane-air mixtures to guarantee stable C_3H_8 ignition through the parametric study.

As wall thermal conductivity is decreased, the concentration of H_2 required decreases. However, this variation trend is not monotonic. Such as inlet velocity of 4 m/s, as the wall thermal conductivity is decreased until 6 $W/m \cdot K$, the minimum concentration of H_2 required decreases monotonically. However, as the wall thermal conductivity is further decreased to 0.5 $W/m \cdot K$, the minimum concentration of H_2 required increases slightly and then continue to decrease. Similar variation trends can be observed for the inlet velocities of 2 and 8 m/s as well. The main reason for the non-monotonic behavior depends on two competitive factors: the rate of the heat (wall) loss to the ambient air vs. the rate of the heat (wall and exhaust gas of burned hydrogen) transfer to the unburned fuel (propane) from hydrogen-air switch to propane-air for different wall thermal conductivity.

3.2 Transient response and ignition characteristics

Fig. 4 Effect of wall thermal conductivity on H_2 cut-off time, C_3H_8 ignition time, 99% C_3H_8 conversion and steady state time in the sequential feed mode. $\phi(H_2) = 0.148$, $\phi(C_3H_8, \text{ after } H_2 \text{ cut-off}) = 0.7$, $u_0 = 2 \text{ m/s}$, $h = 20 \text{ W/m}^2 \cdot K$, and $k_s = 20 \text{ W/m} \cdot K$.

In the sequential feed mode, the effect of wall thermal conductivity on the H_2 cut-off time, C_3H_8 ignition time, 99% C_3H_8 conversion and steady state time are shown in Fig. 4. For three different wall thermal conductivities (0.5, 20 and 200 $W/m \cdot K$), the temporal variations in bulk gas phase temperature, interior wall temperature and C_3H_8 conversion profiles are shown in Fig. 5-7. The flow is switched from hydrogen-air to propane-air mixtures as the exit wall temperatures in micro-combustor exceed the corresponding temperatures shown in Fig. 3 (b). The switch is represented as circles in Fig. 4 and by blue lines in Fig. 5. The H_2 cut-off times do not vary significantly ($40s \leq t_{cut-off} \leq 60s$) with increasing the wall thermal conductivity. For all cases, C_3H_8 ignition times require less than 10 s and 99% C_3H_8 conversion is reached (as observed in Fig. 4) in a short time thereafter once the flow of propane-air mixtures is started. However, compared with lower-conductivity walls, the times taken to reach steady state are

significantly higher for highly-conductivity walls. For low and moderate conductive walls (0.5 and 20 W/m·K) as observed in Fig. 5-7, the ignition characteristics are similar to partially preheating the initial segment of the micro-combustor. However, for high wall thermal conductivity values (200 W/m·K), the ignition characteristics are close to completely heating the micro-combustor wall, and the back-end ignition (similar to fully preheated wall case [47, 48]) can be observed.

(a) $k_s = 0.5 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

(b) $k_s = 20 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

(c) $k_s = 200 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

Fig. 5 Transient response of bulk gas phase temperature profiles in the sequential feed mode for different wall thermal conductivities. $\phi(\text{H}_2) = 0.148$, $\phi(\text{C}_3\text{H}_8, \text{ after H}_2 \text{ cut-off}) = 0.7$, $u_0 = 2 \text{ m/s}$, $h = 20 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$, and $k_s = 20 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$.

(a) $k_s = 0.5 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

(b) $k_s = 20 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

(c) $k_s = 200 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

Fig. 6 Transient response of interior wall temperature profiles in the sequential feed mode for different wall thermal conductivities. $\phi(\text{H}_2) = 0.148$, $\phi(\text{C}_3\text{H}_8, \text{ after H}_2 \text{ cut-off}) = 0.7$, $u_0 = 2 \text{ m/s}$, $h = 20 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$, and $k_s = 20 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$.

(a) $k_s = 0.5 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

(b) $k_s = 20 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

(c) $k_s = 200 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$

Fig. 7 Transient response of C_3H_8 conversion profiles in the sequential feed mode for different wall thermal conductivities. $\varphi(\text{H}_2) = 0.148$, $\varphi(\text{C}_3\text{H}_8, \text{ after H}_2 \text{ cut-off}) = 0.7$, $u_0 = 2 \text{ m/s}$, $h = 20 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$, and $k_s = 20 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$.

In the sequential feed mode, the cumulative C_3H_8 emissions and exit gas temperature for different wall thermal conductivities are shown in Fig. 8. Initially, there are no C_3H_8 emissions until C_3H_8 flow is started as observed in Fig. 8 (a). The C_3H_8 emissions with sharp jump occurs between the switch time and 99% C_3H_8 conversion time (represented as circles in Fig. 8 (a)). Moreover, as the inlet flow is switched from lean hydrogen-air ($\varphi_{\text{H}_2} = 0.148$) to propane-air ($\varphi_{\text{C}_3\text{H}_8} = 0.7$) mixtures, the exit gas temperature increases rapidly. For high thermal conductivity walls (200 $\text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}$), Net C_3H_8 emissions (22.84 mg) at the end of 200 s increased by 3 times for low thermal conductivity walls (5.54 mg (0.5 $\text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}$) and 5.58 mg (20 $\text{W/m}\cdot\text{K}$)).

(a) Cumulative C_3H_8 emissions

(b) Exit gas temperature

Fig. 8 Cumulative C_3H_8 emissions and exit gas temperature in the sequential feed mode for different wall thermal conductivities. $\varphi(\text{H}_2) = 0.148$, $\varphi(\text{C}_3\text{H}_8, \text{ after H}_2 \text{ cut-off}) = 0.7$, $u_0 = 2 \text{ m/s}$, $h = 20 \text{ W/m}^2\cdot\text{K}$, and $k_s = 20 \text{ W/m}\cdot\text{K}$. Circles represent the time taken to reach 99% C_3H_8 conversion in panel (a).

The cumulative amount of H_2 and the time required for C_3H_8 catalytic ignition as a function of H_2 concentration in the co-feed and sequential feed modes are shown in Fig. 9. The co-feed mode entails simultaneously turning on the flow of hydrogen, propane, and air until the propane ignites, and then turning off the hydrogen flow and increasing the flow rates of propane and air so that the total flow rate remains constant throughout the experiment. The cumulative amount of H_2 is defined as the total H_2 amount supplied from the beginning to characteristic ignition temperature [19]. As observed in Fig. 9, the cumulative amount of H_2 and the time required for C_3H_8 catalytic ignition both decrease rapidly with increasing H_2 concentration. For the 0.02 H_2 concentration (on a molar basis), the times required to reach the ignition of C_3H_8 are 9.6 (co-feed mode) and 10.2 (sequential feed mode) times longer than those of mixtures containing 0.06 hydrogen. Similar to aforementioned behavior, for the 0.02 H_2 concentration, the cumulative amounts of H_2 are 3.2 (co-feed mode) and 3.4 (sequential feed mode) times longer than those of mixtures containing 0.06 hydrogen. Therefore, from both the ignition time viewpoint and minimum utilization of H_2 , flows with higher H_2 concentration are desirable. These results are consistent with the conclusions from the previous works of Norton and Vlachos [17], and Zhong *et al.* [19-21] who used n-butane as fuel.

Fig. 9 The cumulative amount of hydrogen and the time required for propane catalytic ignition as a function of hydrogen

concentration in the co-feed and sequential feed modes. Co-feed mode: ϕ (C_3H_8) = 0.7, sequential feed mode: ϕ (C_3H_8 , after H_2 cut-off) = 0.7, $u_0 = 2$ m/s, $h = 20$ W/m²·K, and $k_s = 20$ W/m·K.

In the co-feed mode, although C_3H_8 inhibits the H_2 ignition at short times [17], C_3H_8 ignites as soon as the ignition temperature is reached, leading to a faster heatup (shorter ignition time as observed in Fig. 9) of the micro-combustor as compared to the sequential feed mode. Through external controls and optimization, the ignition time for introducing propane in the sequential feed mode may be improved. However, the co-feed mode (simultaneous starting of flows) is simple, easy to operate, and has the additional benefit of heat release from both fuels (H_2 and C_3H_8). Therefore, the co-feed mode appears to be preferred. These results are consistent with the conclusions from the previous work of Norton and Vlachos [17], who compared the co-feed mode with the swapping mode.

Conclusions

In this study, hydrogen-assisted self-ignition of propane-air mixtures in the sequential feed mode (switched from hydrogen-air to propane-air mixtures) were investigated numerically in Pt/ γ - Al_2O_3 catalytic micro-combustors. The following conclusions were obtained from this micro-scale combustion characteristics study.

- ❖ The wall thermal conductivity, inlet velocity, and inlet equivalence ratio of propane-air mixtures have significant effect on the concentration of H_2 required for C_3H_8 self-ignition in the micro-combustors. In general, the concentration of H_2 required for C_3H_8 self-ignition increased with increasing wall thermal conductivity, decreasing inlet velocity, and decreasing inlet equivalence ratio of propane-air mixtures, while this behavior is existent at higher high-thermal-conductivity ($k_s > 30$ W/m·K) for wall thermal conductivity and inlet velocity.
- ❖ The time taken to reach steady state, the H_2 cut-off time, the C_3H_8 self-ignition time and the cumulative C_3H_8 emissions increased with increasing wall thermal conductivity.
- ❖ For low and moderate conductive walls (0.5 and 20 W/m·K), the self-ignition characteristics are similar to partially preheating the initial segment of the micro-combustor. However, for high wall thermal conductivity values (200 W/m·K), the self-ignition characteristics are close to completely heating the micro-combustor wall, and the back-end ignition can be observed.
- ❖ Higher hydrogen concentrations result in minimum hydrogen utilization and a relatively fast startup of the system, and the co-feed mode of hydrogen-assisted self-ignition is a good startup strategy compared to the sequential feed mode.

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